

MECHANICAL COMPOSITION, WATER-PHYSICAL AND AGROCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF IRRIGATED SIEROZEM-MEADOW SOILS IN SYRDARYA REGION

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Abstract. *In this article, the results of the study of the mechanical composition, water-physical and agrochemical properties of irrigated sierozem-meadow soils of Syrdarya region are presented. Based on a detailed study and monitoring of the general mechanical composition of the soils of the study area, scientifically based measures and recommendations for their improvement have been developed, recommendations for conclusion and implementation have been given.*

Keywords: *mechanical composition of soil, land and water resources, mechanical elements, humus, nitrogen, phosphorus, filtration waters, salinization, salt reserves.*

Introduction. Currently, as a result of measures taken to improve the regulation of land relations, increase the fertility and productivity of soils in our country, a number of positive results are achieved in the field of agriculture in matters of melioration and use of irrigated land.

Rational use of land and water resources of irrigated lands, systematic increase in the yield of agricultural crops and the quality of the harvested crop by restoring, preserving and increasing soil fertility is one of the urgent tasks of our time.

Usually, the irrigation and fertilization system is designed and implemented taking into account the mechanical structure of the soil. The mechanical composition of the soil is one of its main indicators. Many soil properties depend on its mechanical composition. The most important of them are water, food, air, salt and thermal regimes [1-4].

The amount of nutrients in the soil, field moisture capacity, water permeability, absorption capacity, density, air exchange, and mineralogical composition depend on the mechanical structure of the soil [5-7]. Therefore, it is important to know the mechanical composition of the soil. The mechanical composition of the soil is taken into account when washing saline irrigated sierozem-meadow soils. After all, the mechanical composition has a significant effect on the water permeability and water-holding capacity of the soil, and the amount of salts changes depending on the mechanical composition of the soil [7-8]. Based on this, it is necessary to correctly and promptly carry out all agrotechnical and melioration measures, and for this purpose, by studying and re-analyzing the properties of the soil, its mechanical composition, develop scientifically based proposals and recommendations [1-2].

Selected object, purpose and methods of research

Research work is carried out to monitor the mechanical, water-physical and agrochemical properties of irrigated sierozem-meadow soils, as well as land reclamation, condition and its rational use in Mirzaabad district of Syrdarya region.

During the research, genetic-geographical, lithological-geomorphological, comparative chemical-analytical and profile methods were used. To assess the permeability of the soil, the N.A. Kachinsky scale was used. When conducting field, laboratory and office work, the methods

recommended in the manual "Guide to evidence of chemical and agrophysical analysis of soils during land monitoring" by Bairova A.Zh., Tashkuziev M.M. and others [9] were used. The research is planned for 2022-2024, and in the first year, the water-physical and agrochemical properties of the soil, as well as the melioration state of the main soil plots located in the irrigated areas of the farm, were studied. Field experiments and laboratory methods were used for this.

Results and discussion

As the sizes of mechanical elements in the soil decrease, their properties also change. Such sharp changes are especially well expressed at the boundary of the fractions "physical sand" (> 0.01 mm) and "physical clay" (< 0.01 mm). Therefore, when studying the mechanical composition of the soil, special attention was paid to the amount of these particles.

Gray-meadow soils, common in the irrigated areas of Mirzaabad district, are predominantly sandy in mechanical composition, with layers with light and medium loamy alternating towards the lower layers, the amount of physical clay (particles less than 0.01 mm) is 16.2-20.4% sufficient. A characteristic feature of these soils is the predominance of large dust fractions (0.05-0.01 mm), their content in the soil profile varies within 30.4-52.2%, which is a characteristic feature of all Mirzachul soils. The main reason for this is that the soil is loess, and the amount of clay particles was 2.4-6.1% (Table 1). It is known in the literature that the presence of large dust particles in the soil worsens the permeability and water supply of the soil, increases the capillarity of the soil (i.e. the rise of water through capillaries) [3]. U. Toshbekov and A. Altmishev found that the rise of water through capillaries increases from sand, through sand to loess-like sand [5]. This, in turn, accelerates secondary salinization when filtration waters are located nearby.

Table 1. Mechanical composition of soils in selected areas for research

Layer depth, cm.	Fraction size, mm, quantity, %.							Physical clay	soil properties by mechanical composition
	sand			dust		silt			
	>0,25	0,25-0,1	0,1-0,05	0,05-0,01	0,01-0,005	0,005-0,001	<0,001	<0,01	
0-28	5,5	0,5	8,2	52,2	2,1	10,7	3,4	16,2	sandy
28-45	2,5	1,0	10,1	50,8	4,3	11,4	6,1	19,8	sandy
45-96	1,0	10,0	10,4	45,3	2,6	11,0	2,4	16,0	sandy
96-128	0,5	8,0	17,9	30,4	5,1	10,4	3,0	18,5	sandy
128-167	0,5	6,0	10,5	37,0	3,8	14,0	2,6	20,4	light sandy
167-197	1,0	8,0	10,7	43,3	14,5	19,5	3,0	37,0	medium sandy

The amount of humus in these agricultural soils is 0.99-1.38%, with low mobile nitrogen (18-29 mg/kg) and phosphorus (13-25 mg/kg), exchangeable potassium (105-176 mg/kg) and low humus content (Table 2).

In soil formation, especially in salinization processes, filtration waters have a great influence, they determine the rate of formation of water-salt regimes, and in conditions of soil salinization they serve as a means of movement and redistribution. The closer the groundwater level is to the surface and the higher its mineralization, the faster the processes of salt accumulation

and secondary salinization in the soil occur. This process, in turn, depends on the state of existing irrigation and drainage systems, the level of drainage of the area and irrigation standards, in a word, the critical depth of filtration waters. In the study area, the level of infiltration waters fluctuated greatly during the growing season, before irrigation it decreased to 210-240 cm, and after irrigation it increased to 140-170 cm. In the fall, after the completion of irrigation work, the level of seepage waters decreased to 250-300 cm. The amplitude of seasonal fluctuations was 110-130 cm. The composition of the Sizot waters is predominantly sulfate and chloride-sulfate by anions, magnesium-calcium and sodium-calcium mineralization by cations. Gray-meadow soils common in the study area have different degrees of salinization, and the distribution of salts in the soil layers and the thickness of the saline layer are different. Sometimes, almost in the same, high amount, profiled salinization or distribution of salts in all soil layers down to groundwater is observed (Table 3).

Table 2. Agrochemical indicator of soils in the zone selected for the study

Layer depth, cm.	Amount of nutrients			
	amount of humus in the soil, %	N, mg/kg	P ₂ O ₅ , mg/per100 gr, or mg/kg	K ₂ O, mg/per100 gr, or mg/kg
0-28	0,99	22	20	175
28-45	0,86	19	18	146
45-96	0,66	18	13	105

The total amount of salts (dry residue) in the upper soil layer of 0-200 cm was 1.26-1.38%. Including chlorides 0.035-0.049%, sulfates 0.669-0.776%. According to the salinization mechanism, these soils mainly belong to the sulfate-sodium-calcium type of salinization. The amount of gypsum was 3.80-8.91%, carbonates - 2.27-9.56%, general patterns of distribution along the soil profile were not observed. The main place in the qualitative composition of salts is occupied by CaSO₄, followed by MgSO₄ and Na₂SO₄. MgCl₂ and CaCl₂ were very small in the soil layers. NaCl was 0.058-0.091% (Table 3).

Table -3. The amount of water-soluble salts, gypsum and carbonates in the soils of the area selected for research, %

Layer depth, cm.	Dry residue	HCO ₃ ⁻	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	Na ⁺	Type of salinization	Gypsum	CO ₂ -carbonates	pH
0-28	1,260	0,027	0,049	0,669	0,245	0,012	0,058	S-N-C	5,20	3,84	7,53
28-45	1,275	0,027	0,049	0,683	0,126	0,018	0,087	S-N-C	6,20	2,27	7,59
45-96	1,268	0,024	0,035	0,728	0,260	0,012	0,059	S-N-C	8,91	4,97	7,64
96-128	1,305	0,018	0,042	0,701	0,203	0,024	0,091	S-N-C	7,65	9,56	7,61
128-167	1,340	0,027	0,045	0,763	0,272	0,021	0,053	S-N-C	3,80	8,77	7,67
167-197	1,383	0,024	0,049	0,776	0,253	0,024	0,076	S-N-C	5,97	6,33	7,68

*Comment: S- sulfated, N- sodium, C- calcium

The salt reserve in the upper arable layer of widely irrigated gray meadow soils in the study area was 49.9 t/ha. In the 0-100 cm layer, it is 173.8 t/ha, the main part of which consists of sulfates (95.9 t/ha) and chlorides (5.9 t/ha). In the 0-200 cm layer, these indicators are proportionally equal to 365.1; it was 202.5 and 12.5 t/ha (Table 4).

Thus, the irrigated gray-meadow soils common in the study area are mostly moderately saline and highly susceptible to salinization. Therefore, it is necessary to regularly carry out

melioration activities in the area. To do this, first of all, it is necessary to develop scientifically based measures and recommendations and implement them in practice based on a detailed study and monitoring of the melioration state of the region's soils.

Table 4. Water-soluble salts in the studied soil quantity and reserve

Layer depth, cm.	Bulk density, g/cm ³	Amount of salts, salt reserve, %			salt reserve, t/ha		
		Dry residue	Cl	CO ₄ ²⁻	Salt aggregate	Cl	CO ₄ ²⁻
0-30	1,32	1,260	0,049	0,669	49,896	1,940	26,492
30-50	1,36	1,272	0,047	0,697	34,598	1,278	18,958
50-100	1,40	1,275	0,039	0,722	89,250	2,730	50,540
0-100	1,36	1,269	0,045	0,696	173,744	5,949	95,991
100-150	1,42	1,327	0,045	0,737	94,217	3,195	52,327
150-200	1,40	1,388	0,048	0,774	97,160	3,360	54,180
0-200	1,39	1,328	0,046	0,736	365,121	12,504	202,498

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